

ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5 zeolite nanocomposite: Synthesis & its application for the sonocatalytic degradation of toxic organic pollutants

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Abstract.

In the present research, the ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5 zeolite as a newly magnetically separable nanocomposite was successfully synthesized by the ultrasonic-assisted solvothermal method. FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD and VSM were applied to fully characterize the as-synthesized nanocomposite. Then, the sonocatalytic performance of ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5 zeolite was investigated on the organic dyes degradation, namely methylene blue (MB), rhodamine B (RhB) and methyl orange (MO) from aqueous solutions for the first time. Multiple analytical factors such as irradiation time, initial dye concentration, process type, catalyst dosage, H₂O₂ concentration, and organic dye type have been fully evaluated to gain the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. Based on the obtained outcomes, the ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5 zeolite sonocatalyst was incredibly able to completely degrade the organic dyes via using the ultrasonic and H₂O₂ agents. The .OH radicals were distinguished as the main reactive species on the sonodegradation process of dyes under US irradiation, as well. Additionally, the reusability of the ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5 zeolite sonocatalyst was investigated, which affirmed that it can be reused up to five runs with almost trivial loss of catalytic activity. In conclusion, the sonocatalytic degradation of organic dyes by the ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5 zeolite sonocatalyst in the presence of US/H₂O₂ system displays a great potential to study further highly removal of organic pollutants from effluent.

Keywords: ZnFe₂O₄/CdS/ZSM-5, Zeolite, Nanocomposite, Organic dyes, Degradation.